

Model simulation of Belousov-Zhabotinskii reaction containing oxalic acid and acetone as mixed organic substrate in CSTR mode

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The present study is an effort to simulate the behavior of the Belousov-Zhabotinskii system containing bromate-Ce^{III}-H₂SO₄-oxalic acid and acetone as a mixed organic substrate system in a CSTR. The model used is a simplified version of Field and Boyd mechanism. The behavior with respect to flow rate and inflow concentrations are depicted as sets of traces showing the variation of [Ce^{IV}]. An effort is made to represent the simulations observed in terms of bifurcation parameters [oxalic acid]₀ and [BrO₃⁻]₀.

After the sensational work of Belousov¹ and Zhabotinskii² on the classical oscillatory reaction, numerous workers have studied this reaction, namely, metal ion catalyzed oxidation of an easily brominated organic substrate by bromate in a strongly acidic media. Field *et al.*³ proposed a detailed mechanism based on the classical reaction with malonic acid as an organic substrate. Rastogi and Verma⁴ discovered the mixed organic substrate. Field and Boyd⁵ gave a detailed mechanism and showed that the experimental values are in good agreement with the simulated results under certain circumstances. Later several authors have reported the behavior experimentally^{6,7} and performed simulation using various models under closed system conditions⁸. However, the basic behavioral properties of non-linear reacting systems would clearly and effectively be studied if they are allowed to take place in open system conditions, namely, in a continuously stirred tank reactor (CSTR)⁹. Experimental as well as simulation work in a CSTR is under progress. The present paper deals with some of our simulation work in the CSTR mode. The model used is a simplified version of the Field-Boyd mechanism suitably modified on the lines of the work by Rastogi and Misra¹⁰, indicating explicitly the oxidation of oxalic acid as well as bromination of acetone.

Reaction mechanism and computation method :

Study of oscillating chemical reactions in CSTR mode involves two or more inflows of reactants and a reactor vessel, which is continuously being stirred and excess of the reaction mixture is let out of the system. The pumping could be done either by peristaltic pump or by a syringe pump. Peristaltic pumps are very versatile though they have an inbuilt defect of pulsating behavior. Smaller the reactor volume, lesser is the amount of flow necessary. However, the

flow data can be scaled so that it can be universalized. The approach is to report the data in terms of inverse of residence time, which is the ratio of reactor volume to the total flow rate. Thus the data could be rationalized irrespective of the reactor volume. In general, two 'equal flows' are utilized so that the inflow concentrations in the reactor will be half of the concentration of each species in the separate flows. Study of the dynamics in CSTR could be made by initially having a batch system in the reactor and this batch system could be converted to the flow system by starting the flows. Another way of studying the dynamics is starting with an empty reactor vessel and studying the dynamics after the CSTR is operating in the flow mode, namely, after filling of the reactor. In other words, the system will show transient behavior of a batch till the vessel is full. Having a small reactor with high flow could reduce this time. Any way, this limitation depends on the facilities available. During simulation however these practical considerations are not neces-

Table 1

BrO ₃ + Br ⁻ + 2 H ⁺	→	HBrO ₂ + HOBr	(1)
HBrO ₂ + Br ⁻ + H ⁺	→	2 HOBr	(2)
BrO ₃ ⁻ + HBrO ₂ + H ⁺	⇌	2 BrO ₂ + H ₂ O	(3)
Ce ³⁺ + BrO ₂ ⁺ + H ⁺	⇌	Ce ⁴⁺ + HBrO ₂	(4)
2 HBrO ₂	→	BrO ₃ ⁻ + Br ⁻ + 2 H ⁺	(5)
Oxalic acid + Ce ⁴⁺	→	Ce ³⁺ + HCO ₂ ⁺	(6)
Ce ⁴⁺ + HCO ₂ ⁺	→	Ce ³⁺ + Inert product	(7)
Oxalic acid + HOBr	→	Br ⁻ + Other product	(8)
HOBr + Br ⁻ + H ⁺	⇌	Br ₂ + H ₂ O	(9)
Acetone + H ⁺	⇌	Enol + H ⁺	(10)
Br ₂ + Enol + H ⁺	→	Br ⁻ + Other products	(11)

Table 2

Field and Boyd	Field and Försterling
$k_1 = 5.0 \text{ M}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$	$k_2 = 3 \times 10^6 \text{ M}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$
$k_6 = 27.5 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$	$k_3 = 42.0 \text{ M}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$
$k_7 = 1 \times 10^6 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$	$k_{-3} = 4.2 \times 10^7 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$
$k_8 = 150 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$	$k_4 = 8 \times 10^4 \text{ M}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$
$k_9 = 8 \times 10^9 \text{ M}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$	$k_{-4} = 8.9 \times 10^3 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$
$k_{-9} = 110.0 \text{ M}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$	$k_5 = 3 \times 10^3 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$
$k_{10} = 8 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$	
$k_{-10} = 21.3 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$	
$k_{11} = 1.03 \times 10^7 \text{ M}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$	

sary. The volume of the reactor is irrelevant as the flow rate is considered in terms of inverse of residence time. So the simulation is done by considering the flow rate, the initial concentrations of various species of the system and the inflow concentration of major reactants.

Table 1 describes this mechanism consisting of 13 chemical species and 11 pseudo-elementary reactions of which 3,4 and 9,10 are reversible. Table-2 contains the corresponding rate constants, which have been taken partly from Field-Boyd⁵ and Field-Försterling⁶. The kinetics of this system in batch can be described by a system of non-linear first order differential equations obtained by applying law of mass action to each step. Such a system of differential equations can be denoted by

$$\frac{dC_i}{dt} = \sum_j \alpha_{ij} R_j \quad (1)$$

where C_i is the concentration of the i -th. species in the reactor at time t , α_{ij} is the stoichiometric coefficient of the i -th. species in the reaction j which proceeds at the rate R_j calculated from mass action kinetics. The activity of H_2O is taken as unity. This set of equations gets modified in a CSTR by the flow terms as follows :

$$\frac{dC_i}{dt} = \sum_j \alpha_{ij} R_j + k_0(C_{i,0} - C_i) \quad (2)$$

where $C_{i,0}$ is the inflow concentration of species i (i.e. immediately after mixing in the reactor but before any reaction has taken place and k_0 the reciprocal of the residence time in the reactor. The dynamics of the system could be obtained by integration of this set of differential equations. Invariably it is found that non-linearity and large difference in the set of rate constants results in a Stiff system of differential equations. Presently, various numerical integrators (software) are available to solve such a system. 'Simulate' is one such software available with us¹¹, which incorporates the pow-

erful Rosenbrock's integrator of Stiff differential systems. The simulate sets up its own differential equations and the result is provided as integrated values, when appropriate mechanism and other initial values of concentrations and flow rate are provided. The error tolerance of integrator is 10^{-7} , initial step-size is 10^{-8} and maximum step size is 2.0.

The computation treats all the species as variables. The advantage of CSTR is that the oscillations can be observed indefinitely if appropriate inflow concentrations and flow rates are maintained. In the CSTR mode there are two important initial conditions (other than the flow rate), namely, the initial concentration of various species in the reactor and inflow concentration, namely, the concentration of various species which would be obtained in the reactor due to the flows. The initial concentration of all the species in the reactor at time zero is considered as $1 \times 10^{-10} \text{ M}$, as the results are not much affected if the value is taken anything lower. The inflow concentrations chosen are $[\text{BrO}_3^-]_0 = 0.02 \text{ M}$, $[\text{oxalic acid}]_0 = 0.07 \text{ M}$, $[\text{H}^+]_0 = 1.5 \text{ M}$, $[\text{acetone}]_0 = 0.03 \text{ M}$, $[\text{Ce}^{\text{III}}]_0 = 0.005 \text{ M}$. This set of inflow concentrations are considered as the standard for determining the behavior of the system with respect to variables.

Results and discussion

The process of oscillation involves the production of bromine due to the oxidation of oxalic acid by bromate and its consumption by bromination of acetone. The overall stoichiometry of the reaction may be written as¹²

where RH is acetone. The mechanism of this process indicated in Table 1 has been analyzed with respect to flow rates. A flow rate $10^{-3}/\text{s}$ has been found suitable for the study of the effect of inflow concentrations. The range of inflow concentrations studied are $[\text{BrO}_3^-]_0 = 0.005 - 0.1 \text{ M}$, $[\text{oxalic acid}]_0 = 0.001 - 0.6 \text{ M}$, $[\text{acetone}]_0 = 0.001 - 0.3 \text{ M}$.

Fig. 1 indicates the traces in the concentration of Ce^{IV} with the variation of flow rate as a function of time for the standard inflow concentrations. It can be noted that there is a transient period of appreciable duration at low flow rates, which vanishes as the flow rate is increased. The concentration of Ce^{IV} increases during this period. At much high flow rates ($10^{-1}/\text{s}$) there is hardly any transient period. At the lowest flow rate ($10^{-5}/\text{s}$), there is one minimum followed by a maximum after which the system does not show any periodic behavior even after many hours. The amplitude of these oscillations ($10^{-7.5}$ to $10^{-4.5}$) does not change much with the flow rate. On the other hand, the frequency increases

Fig. 1. Simulated plots of oscillations in $[Ce^{IV}]$ at different flow rates with initial concentrations of various species at $1 \times 10^{-10} M$; inflow concentrations of major reactants are $[BrO_3^-]_0 = 0.02 M$, $[oxalic\ acid]_0 = 0.07 M$, $[H^+]_0 = 1.5 M$, $[acetone]_0 = 0.03 M$, $[Ce^{III}]_0 = 0.005 M$. Flow rates : (I) 10^{-5} , (II) 10^{-4} , (III) 10^{-3} , (IV) 10^{-2} , (V) $10^{-1}/s$.

as the flow rate is increased.

Fig. 2 indicates the behavior of the various intermediates at a flow rate of $10^{-3}/s$ with other constraints as in Fig. 1. Oscillations in concentrations of appreciable amplitude are observed with all intermediates except HCO_2^+ which shows hardly a ripple. The oscillations could be broadly grouped as (1), Ce^{IV} , BrO_2^+ , $HBrO_2$, (2), $HOBr$, Br_2 , (3), Br^- , (4) enol. The temporal behavior of various species, i.e. the concentrations at few of the extreme values (indicated as 1, 2, 3 in Fig. 2) and the corresponding time are presented in Table 3. Concentrations of the major reactants, namely, oxalic acid, bromate, acetone and Ce^{III} increase with time and attain asymptotically a steady value close to the inflow concentrations at the end of the transient period. A look at the values shows that the increase in $[Br^-]$ succeeds the maximum at points indicated as 1 and 2 in Fig. 2. Again

Fig. 2. Simulated plots of oscillations of different species at a flow rate of $10^{-3}/s$; all other constraints same as in Fig. 1.

the maximum in $[Ce^{IV}]$ nearly coincides with the minimum in $[Br^-]$. At point 2, the duration of high bromide is rather small. As the oscillations continue and stabilize, this duration becomes longer.

Before the flow commences, the concentration of various species in the cell is $10^{-10} M$. After the flow starts, the concentration of some of the species decreases beyond $10^{-10} M$ and again picks up later on. The transient period may be existent till the appearance of the sustained oscillations. As can be noted, the period and amplitude of these oscillations remain unchanged with time. It can, however, be noted that the oscillations in the concentration of $[Ce^{IV}]$ and $[Br^-]$ are opposite in nature, in the sense that the

Table 3

Species	1-peak time	log Conc.	2-peak time	log Conc.	3-peak time	log Conc.	4-peak time	log Conc.
Ce^{4+}	295	-7.256	910	-6.209	1520	-4.583	2170	-4.635
BrO_2^+	290	-8.858	920	-7.699	1510	-6.812	2170	-6.73
$HBrO_2^+$	285	-6.509	925	-5.323	1520	-4.248	2170	-4.114
Br^-	350	-6.352	935	-5.416	1520	-7.225	2170	-7.198
$HOBr$	295	-7.64	920	-6.457	1520	-5.405	2175	-5.148
Br_2	295	-7.107	930	-5.06	1510	-6.785	2145	-7.052
Enol	-	-	930	-7.868	1525	-8.754	2202	-8.95
HCO_2^+	295	-6.413	-	-	-	-	-	-

Peaks indicated in Fig. 2.

Fig. 3. Simulated plots of oscillations of $[\text{Ce}^{IV}]$ and period and amplitude at a flow rate of $10^{-3}/\text{s}$ at different $[\text{BrO}_3^-]_0$. All other constraints same as in Fig. 1. $[\text{BrO}_3^-]_0$: (I) 0.001, (II) 0.006, (III) 0.02, (IV) 0.08 M.

maximum in $[\text{Ce}^{IV}]$ corresponds with the minimum of the bromide.

Fig. 3 represents the traces of $[\text{Ce}^{IV}]$ along with the variation in period and amplitude as $[\text{BrO}_3^-]_0$ is increased with indicated constraints. No oscillations are observed at both high and low $[\text{BrO}_3^-]_0$. Oscillations start for $[\text{BrO}_3^-]_0 = 0.006$ M after a transient period of about 5000 s. This period decreases as we increase $[\text{BrO}_3^-]_0$. At high $[\text{BrO}_3^-]_0$, there is monotonic behavior of high steady state

($[\text{Ce}^{IV}] \approx 10^{-6}$) and at low $[\text{BrO}_3^-]_0$ there is low steady state ($[\text{Ce}^{IV}] \approx 10^{-8}$).

Fig. 4 represents the plots of $[\text{Ce}^{IV}]$ and the variation in period and amplitude as $[\text{acetone}]_0$ is increased with indicated constraints. No oscillations are observed at both high and low values of $[\text{acetone}]_0$. However, it appears that at high and low values of $[\text{acetone}]_0$, the same steady state, namely, the low steady state ($[\text{Ce}^{IV}] \approx 10^{-8}$) exists. At lower values of $[\text{acetone}]_0$, we did not observe any oscillations

Fig. 4. Simulated plots of oscillations of $[\text{Ce}^{IV}]$ and period and amplitude at a flow rate of $10^{-3}/\text{s}$ at different $[\text{acetone}]_0$; all other constraints same as in Fig. 1. $[\text{acetone}]_0$: (I) 0.006, (II) 0.009, (III) 0.03, (IV) 0.02, (V) 0.03 M.

Fig. 5. Simulated plots of oscillations of $[Ce^{IV}]$ and period and amplitude at a flow rate of $10^{-3}/s$ at different $[oxalic\ acid]_0$; all other constraints same as in Fig. 1. $[oxalic\ acid]_0$: (I) 0.003, (II) 0.009, (III) 0.05, (IV) 0.01, (V) 0.06 M.

after the ones indicated in the figures.

Fig. 5 represents the behavior of $[Ce^{IV}]$ and the variation in period and amplitude as $[oxalic\ acid]_0$ is increased with indicated constraints. Here again no oscillations are observed at both high and low values of $[oxalic\ acid]_0$. At high $[oxalic\ acid]_0$, monotonic behavior with low steady state and at low $[oxalic\ acid]_0$, high steady state ($[Ce^{IV}] \approx 10^{-6}$) were observed. At low $[oxalic\ acid]_0$, some oscillations are observed during the initial time which however vanishes as the time increases giving rise to a high steady state.

To obtain a true bifurcation picture of the system showing the appearance of multiple stabilities, hysteresis, etc., one needs to perform simulation with indicated initial constraints and observes the behavior for a sufficient time so that the system shows a steady behavior. After this, the value of the test constraint in predetermined steps is increased and the behavior of the system is observed for a sufficient time. This is continued to the highest value of the test constraint to be studied. At this stage, the value of the test constraint is decreased in the same steps as it was increased. The behavior of the system is now compared to that while the constraint is increased. During this study, a system showing hysteresis behavior will indicate two sets of situations (in some range of the test constraint) during the increase or decrease process.

However, presently, we have performed simulations of

the system at various (high/low) fixed values of the test constraints without involving the hysteresis process. In other words, these simulations pertain to fixed constraints without changing the value of the test constraints after sufficient time for a single initial system. The observations thus obtained are presented in Fig. 6 showing oscillatory and non-oscillatory regions. The bifurcation parameters chosen are $[oxalic\ acid]_0$ and $[BrO_3^-]_0$ at a fixed inflow concentrations

Fig. 6. Behavior of the system in the $[BrO_3^-]_0$ and $[oxalic\ acid]_0$ plane other constraints are $[H^+]_0 = 2.0\ M$, $[Ce^{III}]_0 = 0.008\ M$, $[acetone]_0 = 0.06\ M$, flow rate $10^{-4}/s$.

of $[H^+]_0 = 2.0 M$, $[Ce^{III}]_0 = 0.008 M$, $[acetone]_0 = 0.06 M$ and flow rate is taken as $10^{-4}/s$. The time of observation is of the order of 20000 s and above. The oscillations are observed only in region B and C. At higher value of $[oxalic\ acid]_0$, the system has a long monotonic transient period (region C) before the onset of steady oscillatory behavior. In the dotted portion (region A), the system shows a number of transient oscillations, before it approaches non-oscillatory state.

Our above simulation work, in particular those presented in Figs. 3–5 are in good agreement with that indicated by Rastogi and Misra³ for the batch system, in the sense that there are lower and upper critical concentrations for the appearance/disappearance of oscillations. However, some of our experimental work indicates that the model is not in quantitative agreement and does not show oscillations for the constraints for which experimentally we do observe oscillating behavior. Further work to enlarge and modify the model presented in Table 1 to account for experimental observations is under progress.

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